

Receptive and Productive Skills Online Learning During Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract :- COVID-19 pandemic situation has prevented people from doing their outdoor activities including learning and teaching activities. The challenges faced by EFL classroom lecturers is particularly concerned with the teaching of listening, writing, reading and speaking as part of productive and receptive skills. These skill courses are generally approached using offline system in the classroom which enables the lecturers and the students to have direct interaction. Teaching these courses online would be a challenging task for EFL classroom lecturers as it requires additional technological devices. This study addresses students' experiences in learning listening and speaking in EFL classroom before and during COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, this study can have positive contribution in providing appropriate and productive teaching methods which is applicable for EFL classroom context. The students' experiences are elicited through questionnaire method that are analyzed by means of descriptive qualitative research design. This study showed the crucial differences that need to be taken into account by teaching practitioners in the Indonesian context, particularly in teaching English during the COVID-19 pandemic era.

Keywords:- Online Learning, Covid-19, Listening, Speaking.

I. INTRODUCTION

The escalating of Coronavirus Disease 2019 or Covid-19 spread throughout the world has brought a significant change in almost every way of life. Since the virus is airborne, people are forced to limit their outside activities. There are even some countries that implement the lockdown. Doing the activities at home is highly recommended. Employees work from home; students learn from home. This situation drives people to use digital technology to stay connected to their outside activities. People are more engaged to the gadgets than before. Everything is digitalized to enable people to keep going on their activities during this Covid-19 pandemic.

In Indonesia, financial aspect is the most affected one by the outbreak of Covid-19 virus. Companies are bankrupt and more jobless workers. Along with it, the most clearly impacted aspect is the education. The traditional learning activities which enable lecturers and students to meet face-to-face in the classroom must be changed due to the government's policy that encourage people to limit their outside activity. Lecturers are demanded to implement an adaptive teaching-learning method during Covid-19 pandemic. They must transform the offline learning mode

into online learning mode immediately to be able to conduct the teaching-learning activities. Online learning is the only learning method that assumed applicable in the present situation. Online learning refers to a totally online course which entirely given through the internet (Nguyen, 2015). E-learning is the other term for online learning. E-learning means implementing information and computer technologies to create learning experiences (Coman et al., 2020). The following is the benefits of online learning (Medford, 2004):

- Accessibility: online learning enables learners to study from anywhere as long as they have adequate internet connection.
- Personalized learning: online learning provides an opportunity for the learners to manage his/her own learning. Online learning not only can develop the learners' ICT skill, but also can motivate, improve confidence and self-esteem, overcome problems encountered by the learners, personalize the learning experience, broaden access and improve learning experience.
- Cost-effectiveness: less money is spent in online learning because it does not require travel expenses and it can be done at any geographic places.
- Promotes research: producing sophisticated work motivates students to publish their works, i.e., they post their works on the web as reference for future students.
- Basic computer skills: the learners have the opportunity to improve their technical skills in using ICT which later to be useful in their professional life in the future.
- Equal opportunity to all: in online learning, students are treated equally and given the similar opportunity though they live at a distant place.
- Self-pacing: Learners are able to do their best to finish the assignments without time limit. They are free to complete the work based on their own will without being fear of labelled slow by the others.
- Globalization: in the way of education, geographical barriers are being narrowed by new technologies.

Transforming teaching-learning method from offline mode into online mode is not an effortless action. Lecturers are required to convert all teaching materials and instruments which previously designed for offline learning to be applicable in online learning mode. In online learning, lecturers must ensure the availability of (1) the technology, platforms, equipment and resources, (2) adaptable teaching and learning materials in distant learning, and (3) qualified free educational resources or references that can be accessed both by lecturers or students (Hamid et al., 2020). Converting

teaching-learning method from offline to online learning mode requires the application of technology. Ensuring the availability of appropriate platforms for online learning, the lecturers commonly use virtual meeting application to conduct the virtual class. Basically, virtual class is similar with physical classroom. It was equipped with audio, video, text chat, interactive whiteboard, and screen sharing (Yilmaz, 2015) (Al-Nuaim, 2012). Only, the difference is on the use of devices as the media to perform the virtual class.

For the developed countries, technology is no longer their main issue due to the sophisticated technology system that they own for years. But for a developing country such as Indonesia, technology is surely need to be highlighted in this current situation of Covid-19 pandemic. For instance, internet connection is the main element that should be available to support online learning. To conduct an online learning activity, the primary needs of it, is the adequate internet access and network connection (Nugroho et al., 2020) In fact, there are many students in Indonesia, particularly those who live in rural areas who cannot access or get the satisfactory internet connection. The following are the lacks of disadvantages of online learning (Efriana, 2021) :

1. Lack of learning tools such as students' parents and students do not have computer or android equipped mobile phone.
2. Spending more cost for internet quota. This certainly is a problem for students from middle to lower class economies.
3. Difficult to access the internet network due to the remote places where the students live.
4. Lecturers' unplanned learning method and materials for online learning. The sudden alter from offline to online learning mode leaves the educators must adapt the teaching methods and materials into online learning in a very limited time.
5. Technology cannot displace lecturer's role. Constructing the students' character is not found in the use of technology in education. It only facilitates the transfer knowledge from lecturer to students.

This study investigates the students' experience of EFL classroom in online learning particularly in learning receptive and productive skills namely listening and speaking skills. Listening is called receptive skill because in listening, the learner receives the language. On the other side, speaking is defined as a productive skill due to the resulted output of it such as talks, dialogues, speech, etc. Teaching listening and

speaking skills in online learning mode is challenging because teaching listening and speaking skills can be categorized as an interactive teaching activity. When learners are actively engaged or participated in attempting to communicate, then speaking a second or foreign language will be eased (Nunan, 1991). The engagement of lecturer and student is essential in EFL classroom, particularly in teaching listening and speaking skills. As Stern in Rahayu states that the students' conscious and intentional engagement in learning activities determine the learning effectiveness (Rahayu, 2018)

Finding the right teaching method and application during Covid-19 pandemic is an interesting topic to discuss. Its purpose is to support the continuity of effective teaching-learning activities although in different learning mode namely online learning mode. Therefore, it is important to investigate the students' experience during online learning. Later, based on the students' experiences, an appropriate and productive learning methods can be figured out to be implemented.

II. METHOD

The participants of this study were 35 students of English Literature Study Program in Hasanuddin University. They have experienced both offline and online learning mode in Listening and Speaking and Academic Listening Speaking courses. The respondents were given a questionnaire link which investigated the learning materials, learning activities, type of assignment, lecturer's involvement, students' involvement, lecturer-students engagement, engagement among students, and the challenge of offline and online learning mode. These points that were asked in the questionnaire were divided into two parts namely offline and online learning mode. In addition, this study also investigated the students' preference of learning mode.

Later, the data collected from questionnaire were analyzed descriptively. Thus, this study is categorized as a descriptive qualitative study.

III. FINDINGS

The collected data were divided into two sections into offline learning mode and online learning mode. The subjects that were examined from the participants namely learning material, learning activities, type of assignment, lecturer's involvement, students' involvement, engagement between lecturer and students, and engagement among students.

A. Learning Material

Learning materials from the lecturers namely text book, audio, online sources, and other learning material that applied by the lecturer in offline and online learning mode were investigated.

Questions	Options	Percentage	
		Offline Learning	Online Learning
1. What is/are the material that the lecturer use?	Text book	94	69
	Audio	94	77
	Online sources	46	71
	Other	0	0

Table 1:- Learning Material

The chart shows that text book and audio is the most dominant used learning materials in offline learning mode class of listening and speaking. 94% of the respondents said the lecturer used text book and audio in teaching. Moreover, 46% of the respondents choose online source as learning material and there was no other learning material utilized in listening speaking class.

There was an increase in the use of online sources in the online learning mode. 71% of the respondents were given online sources in their listening and speaking class. While 69% of the respondents used text book and 77% used audio. Beside text book, audio and online sources, there was also no other learning material used in online learning mode.

B. Learning Activities

The learning activities that commonly implemented in listening and speaking class are performing speaking/dialogue, independent listening, group activity/discussion. In the questionnaire, the option of 'other' learning activity was given to provide other learning activities that implemented in listening and speaking class.

Table 2:- Learning Activities

Questions	Options	Percentage	
		Offline Learning	Online Learning
2. What is/are the type of learning activities that applied by the lecturer?	Performing speaking/dialogue	94	46
	Independent listening	71	89
	Group activity/discussion	94	55
	Other	0	3

The students most dominantly performed speaking/dialogue in offline learning mode in listening and speaking class (94%). The second most frequent learning activity was group activity/discussion (91%). In addition, 71% of the respondents experienced independent listening and no other learning activities were performed in listening and speaking class.

In the online learning mode of listening and speaking class, the most frequent learning activity was independent listening (89%). There was a decrease in the implementation of performing speaking/dialogue (46%) and group activity/discussion (55%). The other learning activity applied in online learning mode was personal assignment (3%).

C. Types of Assignment

In this part, the types of assignment that investigated were filling gap (listening task), short-answer question, creating speaking video, creating speaking audio, and other option of assignment type was also provided.

Questions	Options	Percentage	
		Offline Learning	Online Learning
3. What is/are the type of assignment that given by the lecturer?	Filling gap (listening)	86	60
	Short-answer question	83	83
	Creating speaking video	66	63
	Creating speaking audio	46	63
	Other	9	6

Table 3:- Types of Assignment

The given task to 86% percent of the respondents was filling gap (listening task) and 83% of the respondents given short-answer question task. 66% of the respondents did creating speaking video task and 46% of the respondents created speaking audio. The other type of assignment was retelling in front of the class what the respondents had listened (9%).

There was an increase in creating speaking audio task in online learning mode. 63% of the respondents was given this type of assignment during online learning mode. The percentage of short-answer question was similar in offline and online learning mode. Filling gap (listening) use was decreased into 60% and creating speaking video was also decreased into 63%. The other type of assignment given to the respondents in the online learning was group video presentation (6%).

D. Lecturer's Involvement

Beside investigating the teaching instruments (learning materials, learning activities, types of assignment), this study also investigated lecturers' involvement in both offline and online learning mode.

Questions	Options	Percentage	
		Offline Learning	Online Learning
4. How is the lecturer's involvement?	Very actively involved	71	6
	Actively involved	23	60
	Not actively involved	6	31

Table 4:- Lecturer's Involvement

It can be seen in the chart that in offline learning mode, the lecturer was very actively involved (71%) and actively involved (23%) in the listening and speaking class. There was only 6% of the respondents who said that the lecturer was not actively involved.

In online learning mode, the lecturer of listening and speaking course was no longer very actively involved (6%). The lecturer was remained actively involved (60%). Moreover, the lecturer's involvement was decreased (31% of the respondents said the lecturer was not actively involved).

E. Student's Involvement

This part investigated students' involvement in the learning activity during offline and online learning class mode.

Questions	Options	Percentage	
		Offline Learning	Online Learning
5. How is the student's involvement?	Very actively involved	51	6
	Actively involved	49	40
	Not actively involved	0	54

Table 5:- Student's Involvement

The students were very actively involved (51%) and actively involved (49%). There was no student who not actively involved in offline learning mode.

There was a significant change in the students' involvement during online learning mode. The respondents who not actively involved were 54% and 40% of the respondents who remain actively involved. It was only 6% of the respondents who stayed very actively involved.

F. Lecturer and Students Engagement

Based on the collected data, there was a quite meaningful difference of the lecturer and student's engagement in both offline and online learning mode.

Questions	Options	Percentage	
		Offline Learning	Online Learning
6. How is the engagement between the lecturer and the students?	Highly engaged	63	6
	Engaged	34	20
	Low engaged	3	71

Table 6:- Lecturer & Students Involvement

In the offline learning mode of listening and speaking class, the lecturer and the students are highly engaged (63%). 34% of the respondents said the lecturer and students are engaged, and 3% said low engaged.

In the online learning mode, there was a significant change in the engagement between the lecturer and the students. 71% of the respondents stated that the engagement of lecturer and students was low engaged. There were 20% of the respondents who said

that the lecturer and the students were engaged during online learning class. In addition, 6% of the students said the lecturer and the students were highligh engaged in online learning mode.

G. Engagement among Students

The engagement among students in both offline and online learning mode of listening and speaking class was also investigated through the questionnaire.

Questions	Options	Percentage	
		Offline Learning	Online Learning
7. How is the engagement among the students?	Highly engaged	60	6
	Engaged	34	43
	Low engaged	6	51

Table 7:- Engagement among Students

Generally, the students were highly engaged in offline learning mode of listening and speaking class (60%) and engaged (34%). There was 6% of the respondents who said that the engagement among students is low.

Similar with the engagement of the lecturer and students mentioned previously, the engagement of students in online learning mode was significantly change. There was only 6% of the respondents who stated that the students were highly engaged. 43% of the respondents said the students were engaged. While 51% of the respondents stated that the engagement among students was low engaged.

H. Students Learning Mode Preference

Chart 1:- Students Learning Mode Preference

The last point that was asked to the respondents through the questionnaire is the students' preference of learning

IV. DISCUSSIONS

The learning materials that used by the lecturer in teaching listening and speaking were similar in both offline and online learning mode. There was no other learning material beside text book, audio, and online sources that used in this course. It happened due to the limited time given to the lecturer to prepare the appropriate material that was adaptive in online class. The text book was scanned and the file of the scanned text book was given to the students. The materials for listening and speaking activities were integrated in one book. Therefore, the use of audio is almost as frequent as the use of text book. There was an increase in the use of online sources as the learning material. It enabled students to study independently when there was no virtual meeting through meeting apps such as *zoom* or *google meet*. The lecturers rarely held virtual meetings considering the students to keep their internet quota.

mode. The data shows that the students preferred offline learning mode (78%) rather than online learning mode (22%).

The most frequent learning activities in offline learning mode was performing speaking/dialogue and group activity/discussion. It is naturally conducted in listening and speaking class. But, in online learning mode class, performing speaking/dialogue was hard to do. It was possible to perform speaking/dialogue in virtual class, but not all students were encouraged to speak up. In addition, in the virtual class, the students sometimes encountered poor network connection caused by the remote area where they lived. In online learning mode of listening and speaking class, independent listening is the most frequent applied learning activities. In line with the applied learning material mentioned previously in online learning mode, the students were given the audio for them to do the independent listening. This learning activity was implemented because it saved more internet quota than in the other learning activities.

Types of assignments that given more frequently in offline learning were filling gap and short-answer questions. The least frequent form of assignment given in offline

learning class was retelling in front of the class what the students had listened, followed by creating speaking audio. The students were given creating speaking video in both offline and online learning mode. The difference of assignment types in offline and online learning mode class was on the increase number in the use of creating speaking audio in the online learning mode class. After listening the audio, the students were asked to retell what they had listened in the speaking audio. The giving of creating speaking audio as a form of assignment during online learning mode is in line with the previous activities explained in the previous part. The students are encouraged to do more independent learning activities but still under the lecturer's supervision.

Lecturer's and students' involvements were expressively decreased in online learning mode. If the lecturer and students were very actively involved in offline learning mode, the involvement of lecturer and students was very low during the online learning mode. In offline class, the lecturer and students came to the class and did the roles as it used to be. Lecturer as an education facilitator, while students as learners. Since the situation of Covid-19 pandemic, this form of traditional class cannot be done. The lecturer starts the virtual class from home, and the students join the virtual class at their homes too. Either the lecturer or students has some classes. It is impossible for the lecturer to conduct virtual meeting for all classes. Meanwhile, students will spend more internet quota to join the virtual classes. Thus, sometimes the lecturer limits the duration of virtual class, i.e., the lecturer conducts virtual class to give assignment and a brief explanation about the given assignment. Even, the lecture only gives the assignment to the students and its instruction through chat application such as *Whatsapp* or *Telegram*. The involvements of lecturer and students are restricted only to discuss about the assignment.

Similar with lecturer's and students' involvements, the engagement of lecturer-students and students-students was very low in the online learning mode of listening and speaking class. It was caused by the limited space shared by the lecturer and students. In the traditional offline class, the lecturer was able to roam around the classroom to interact closely with students. So, the lecturer and students were very engaged. So did the engagement among students. The meeting in the classroom allowed the students to actively interact each other, have chit-chat, participate in the class or small group discussion, etc. Thus, the engagement among students was very high. While in online learning mode class, the crowd of the class was rarely found. In online class, the lecturer and students met virtually. Not all students were shown on one screen of the virtual meeting app. Additionally, there were only some students who turned their video on during the virtual class. Also, not all students have the opportunity to speak up in the virtual class. It was either because the students were not confident to speak in English or they encounter some technical problem such as poor internet connection which hamper them to involve actively in the virtual class discussion.

At last, regarding all the issues that encountered in the online learning mode, the students preferred to have offline learning mode instead of online learning mode. The reasons for choosing offline learning mode over online learning mode include poor network connection, limited internet quota, low engagement of lecturer and students, and lack of interaction between lecturer and students.

V. CONCLUSION

Covid-19 pandemic brings a challenging improvement in education, particularly in receptive and productive skills courses. In the online learning mode, the lecturers and students must deal and cope with the technology issue namely internet connection and quota. Besides, the educators also need training to provide interactive teaching instruments for the online learning mode class to keep the involvement and engagement of lecturers and students as high as in the offline learning mode class.

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